

Runtime Data Center Temperature Prediction using Grammatical Evolution Techniques

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Abstract

Data Centers are huge power consumers, both because of the energy required for computation and the cooling needed to keep servers below thermal redlining. The most common technique to minimize cooling costs is increasing data room temperature. However, to avoid reliability issues, and to enhance energy efficiency, there is a need to predict the temperature attained by servers under variable cooling setups. Due to the complex thermal dynamics of data rooms, accurate runtime data center temperature prediction has remained as an important challenge. By using Grammatical Evolution techniques, this paper presents a methodology for the generation of temperature models for data centers and the runtime prediction of CPU and inlet temperature under variable cooling setups. As opposed to time costly Computational Fluid Dynamics techniques, our models do not need specific knowledge about the problem, can be used in arbitrary data centers, re-trained if conditions change and have negligible overhead during runtime prediction. Our models have been trained and tested by using traces from real Data Center scenarios. Our results show how we can fully predict the temperature of the servers in a data rooms, with prediction errors below 2°C and 0.5°C in CPU and server inlet temperature respectively.

Keywords: Temperature prediction; Data Centers; Energy efficiency

1. Introduction

Data Centers are found in every sector of the economy and provide the computational infrastructure to support a wide range of applications, from traditional applications to High-Performance Computing or Cloud services. Over the past decade, both the computational capacity of data centers and the number of these facilities have increased tremendously without relative and proportional energy efficiency, leading to unsustainable costs [1]. In 2010, data center electricity represented 1.3% of all the electricity use in the world, and 2% of all electricity use in the US [2]. In year 2012, global data center power consumption increased to 38GW, and in year 2013 there was a further rise of 17% to 43GW [3].

The cooling needed to keep the servers within reliable thermal operating conditions is one of the major contributors to data center power consumption, and accounts for over 30% of the electricity bill [4] in traditional air-cooled infrastructures. In the last years, both industry and academia have devoted significant effort to decrease the cooling power, increasing data center Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE), defined as the ratio between total facility power and IT power. According to a report by the Uptime Institute, average PUE improved from 2.5 in 2007 to 1.65 in 2013 [5], mainly due to more efficient cooling systems and higher data room ambient temperatures.

However, increased room temperatures reduce the safety margins to CPU thermal redlining and may cause potential reliability problems. To avoid server shutdown, the maximum CPU temperature limits the minimum cooling. The key question of how to set the supply temperature of the cooling system to ensure the worst-case scenario, is still to be clearly answered [6]. Most data centers typically operate with server inlet temperatures ranging between 18°C and 24°C, but we can find some of them as cold as 13°C [7], and others as hot as 35°C [8]. These values are often chosen based on conservative suggestions provided by manufacturers, and ensure inlet temperatures within the ranges published by ASHRAE (i.e., 15°C to 32°C for enterprise servers [9]).

Data center designers have collided with the lack of accurate models for the energy-efficient real-time management of computing facilities. One modeling barrier in these scenarios is the high number of variables potentially correlated with temperature that prevent the development of macroscopic analytical models. Nowadays, to simulate the inlet temperature of servers under certain cooling conditions, designers rely on time consuming and very expensive Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations. These techniques use numerical methods to solve the differential equations that drive the thermal dynamics of the data room. They need to consider a comprehensive number of parameters both from the server and the data room (i.e. specific characteristics of servers such as airflow rates, data room dimensions and setup). Moreover, they are not robust to changes in the data center (i.e. rack placement and layout changes, server turn-off, inclusion of new servers, etc.). If

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54 the simulation fails to properly incorporate a relevant param-
 55 eter, or if there is a deviation between the theoretical and the
 56 real values, the simulation becomes inaccurate. Due to the high
 57 economic and computational cost of CFD simulation, models
 58 cannot be re-run each time there is a change in the data room.

59 To minimize cooling costs, the development of models that
 60 accurately predict the CPU temperature of the servers under
 61 variable environmental conditions is a major challenge. These
 62 models need to work on runtime, adapting to the changing con-
 63 ditions of the data room automatically re-training if data center
 64 conditions change dramatically, and enabling data center oper-
 65 ators to increase room temperature safely.

66 The nature of the problem suggests the usage of meta-
 67 heuristics instead of analytical solutions. Meta-heuristics make
 68 few assumptions about the problem, providing good solutions
 69 even when they have fragmented information. Some meta-
 70 heuristics such as Genetic Programming (GP) perform Feature
 71 Engineering (FE), a particularly useful technique to select the
 72 set of features and combination of variables that best describe
 73 a model. Grammatical Evolution (GE) is an evolutionary com-
 74 putation technique based on GP used to perform symbolic re-
 75 gression [10]. This technique is particularly useful to provide
 76 solutions that include non-linear terms offering Feature Engi-
 77 neering capabilities and removing analytical modeling barriers.
 78 Also, designer’s expertise is not required to process a high vol-
 79 ume of data as GE is an automatic method. However, GE pro-
 80 vides a vast space of solutions that may need to be bounded to
 81 achieve algorithm efficiency.

82 This paper develops a data center room thermal modeling
 83 methodology based on GE to predict on runtime, and with suf-
 84 ficient anticipation, the critical variables that drive reliability
 85 and cooling power consumption in data centers. Particularly,
 86 the main contributions of our work are the following:

- 87 • The development of multi-variable models that incorpo-
 88 rate time dependence based on Grammatical Evolution
 89 to predict CPU and inlet temperature of the servers in a
 90 data room during runtime. Due to the feature engineering
 91 and symbolic regression performed by GE, our models incor-
 92 porate the optimum selection of representative features
 93 that best describe the thermal behavior.
- 94 • We prevent premature convergence by means of Social
 95 Disaster Techniques and Random Off-Spring Generation,
 96 dramatically reducing the number of generations needed
 97 to obtain accurate solutions. We tune the models by sel-
 98 lecting the optimum parameters and fitness function using
 99 a reduced experimental setup, consisting of real measure-
 100 ments taken from a single server isolated in a fully sen-
 101 sorized data room.
- 102 • We offer a comparison with other techniques commonly
 103 used in literature to solve temperature modeling problems,
 104 such as autoregressive moving average (ARMA) mod-
 105 els, linear model identification methods (N4SID), and dy-
 106 namic neural networks (NARX).
- 107 • The proposal of an automatic data room thermal model-
 108 ing methodology that scales our solution to a realistic Data

Figure 1: Typical raised-floor air-cooled Data Center layout

Center scenario. As a case study, we model CPU and in-
 let temperatures using real traces from a production data
 center.

Our work allows the generation of accurate temperature models
 able to work on runtime and adapt to the ever changing con-
 ditions of these scenarios, while achieving very low average
 errors of 2°C for CPU temperature and 0.5°C for inlet tem-
 perature.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2
 accurately describes the modeling problem, whereas Section 3
 provides an overview of the current solutions. Section 4 de-
 scribes our proposed solution, whereas Section 5 presents the
 experimental methodology. Section 6 shows the results ob-
 tained and Section 7 discusses them. Finally, Section 8 con-
 cludes the paper.

2. Problem description

2.1. Data room thermal dynamics

To ensure the safe operation of a traditional raised-floor air-
 cooled Data Center, data rooms are equipped with chilled-water
 Computer Room Air Conditioning (CRAC) units that use con-
 ventional air-cooling methods. Servers are mounted in racks on
 a raised floor. Racks are arranged in alternating cold/hot aisles,
 with server inlets facing cold air and outlets creating hot aisles.
 CRAC units supply air at a certain temperature and air flow rate
 to the Data Center through the floor plenum. The floor has some
 perforated tiles through which the blown air comes out. Cold
 air refrigerates servers and heated exhaust air is returned to the
 CRAC units via the ceiling, as shown in Figure 1.

Even though this solution is very inefficient in terms of en-
 ergy consumption, the majority of the data centers use this
 mechanism. In fact, despite the recent advances in high-density
 cooling techniques, according to a survey by the Uptime Insti-
 tute, in 2012 only 19% of large scale data centers had incor-
 porated other cooling mechanisms [5]. In some scenarios, the
 control knob of the cooling subsystem is the cold air supply
 temperature, whereas in others, it is the return temperature of
 the heated exhaust air to the CRAC unit.

The maximum IT power density that can be deployed in the
 Data Center is limited by the perforated tile airflow. Because
 the plenum is usually obstructed (e.g. blocked with cables in
 some areas), a non-uniform airflow distribution is generated and
 each tile exhibits a different pressure drop. Moreover, in data
 centers where the hot and cold aisles are not isolated, which is

152 the most common scenario, the heated exhaust air recirculates
153 to the cold aisle, mixing with the cold air.

154 2.2. Temperature-energy tradeoffs

155 The factor limiting minimum data room cooling is maximum
156 server CPU temperature. Temperatures higher than 85°C can
157 cause permanent reliability failures [11]. At temperatures above
158 95°C, servers usually turn off to prevent thermal redlining. Pre-
159 vious work on server power and thermal modeling [12], shows
160 how CPU temperature is dominated by: i) power consumption,
161 which is dependent on workload execution, ii) fan speed, which
162 changes the cooling capacity of the server, and iii) server cold
163 air supply (inlet temperature).

164 Thus, to keep all the equipment under normal operation,
165 CRAC units have to supply the air at an adequately low temper-
166 ature to ensure that all CPU's are below the critical threshold.
167 However, inlet temperature is also not uniform across servers.
168 The cold air temperature at the server inlet depends on several
169 parameters: i) the CRAC cold air supply, ii) the airflow rate
170 through the perforated tiles, and iii) the outlet temperature of
171 adjacent servers due to air recirculation.

172 Setting the cooling air supply temperature to a low value,
173 even though ensures safety operation, implies increased power
174 consumption due to a larger burden on the chiller system. The
175 goal of energy-efficient cooling strategies is to increase the cold
176 air supply temperature without reaching thermal redlining. Due
177 to the non-linear efficiency of cooling systems, lowering air
178 supply temperature can yield important energy savings. A met-
179 ric widely used is that each degree of increase in air supply
180 temperature yields 4% energy savings in the cooling subsys-
181 tem [13]. To increase air supply temperature safely, however,
182 we need to predict not only the inlet temperature to the servers,
183 but also the CPU temperature that each server attains under the
184 current workload.

185 Due to the temperature gradients between hot and cold aisles
186 and the data room layout and geometry, the air inside a data cen-
187 ter behaves like a turbulent fluid. Thus, obtaining an analytical
188 relation between cold air supply and server inlet temperature is
189 not trivial, making inlet and CPU temperature prediction a chal-
190 lenging problem. Besides, data centers are composed of thou-
191 sands of CPU cores, whose temperatures need to be modeled
192 independently. This prevents the usage of classical regression
193 techniques that need human interaction to train and validate the
194 models.

195 3. Literature overview

196 Data center room thermal modeling enables both thermal
197 emergency management and energy optimization, and enhances
198 reliability. Because of the turbulent behavior of the air in the
199 Data Center room, Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simu-
200 lation has traditionally been the most commonly used solution
201 in both industry and academia [14].

202 CFD is used to model the inlet and outlet temperature of
203 servers, given cold air supply parameters, room layout, server
204 configuration and utilization, in order to either optimize cooling

205 costs or detect hot spots [15]. CFD solvers perform a three-
206 dimensional numerical analysis of the thermodynamic equa-
207 tions that govern the data room. Their main drawbacks is that
208 they require and expert to configure the simulation, and are
209 computationally costly both in the modeling stage (i.e. mod-
210 eling a small-sized data room may take from hours to days)
211 and in the evaluation phase, thus preventing their online usage.
212 Moreover, CFD simulation is not robust to changes in the layout
213 of the Data Center, i.e. server placement, open tiles, workload
214 running or cold air supply setting.

215 To solve these issues, Chen et.al. [16] use CFD together with
216 sensor information to calibrate the simulation and reduce com-
217 putational complexity. Their work achieves a prediction error
218 below 2°C when predicting temperature 10 minutes in ad-
219 vance. Other work [17] presents the Data Center as a distributed
220 Cyber-Physical System (CPS) in which both computational and
221 physical parameters can be measured with the goal of minimiz-
222 ing energy consumption. Our work leverages this concept by
223 using a monitoring system [18] capable of collecting environ-
224 mental (i.e. cold air supply and server inlet temperature, air-
225 flow, etc.) and server data (i.e. temperature, power, fan speed,
226 etc.) from a real data center.

227 A common alternative to CFD are abstract heat flow models.
228 These models characterize the steady state of hot air recircu-
229 lation inside the data center. Recirculation is described by a
230 cross-interference coefficient matrix which denotes how much
231 of every node's outlet heat contributes to the inlet of every other
232 node. This matrix is obtained in an offline profiling stage using
233 CFD [19]. Even though profiling is still costly, model evalua-
234 tion can be performed online.

235 Machine learning techniques have also been used in Data
236 Center modeling. The Weatherman [20] tool uses neural net-
237 works to predict the inlet temperature of servers, obtaining pre-
238 diction errors below 1°C in over 90% of their traces. How-
239 ever, they use simulation traces obtained with CFD simulation
240 for their training and test sets, instead of real data. The prob-
241 lem behind time series prediction can be explained as a prob-
242 lem of extracting a manageable set of adequate features, fol-
243 lowed by a regression mechanism. Careful selection of features
244 and their horizon is therefore of much greater importance com-
245 pared with the static-data prediction problem. Neural network-
246 based approaches require previous knowledge of the parame-
247 ters that drive thermal modeling, obtaining them using pseudo-
248 exhaustive algorithms. Our work, on the contrary, relies on the
249 benefits of feature engineering in Symbolic Regression prob-
250 lems to obtain the relevant features and construct the models in
251 an automated way.

252 The work by De Silva *et al.* [21] is the one most similar to
253 ours, regarding the modeling methodology. The authors use
254 Grammatical Evolution for electricity load prediction. As op-
255 posed to our work, this paper is focused on predicting the trend,
256 momentum and volatility indicators of a timeseries, not on ob-
257 taining a physical model, i.e. they do not solve a multi-variable
258 problem.

259 In summary, the main issues in all previous approaches are:
260 i) they monitor and predict inlet temperature instead of CPU
261 temperature, ii) modeling is performed for only certain hand-

262 picked cooling and workload configurations, iii) the use of CPU
 263 utilization as a proxy for server power, iv) they assume data
 264 centers with homogeneous servers, v) server fan speed is con-
 265 sidered constant, vi) results are not validated with real traces,
 266 and vii) model construction requires specific knowledge on the
 267 problem and classical feature selection, which prevents the us-
 268 age of automated techniques.

269 Our work, on the contrary, first predicts inlet temperature and
 270 then uses this result to predict CPU temperature, which is the
 271 factor limiting cooling. Both in our training and test sets, we
 272 use real traces obtained from enterprise servers in a data cen-
 273 ter. Moreover, as shown in previous work [12], in highly multi-
 274 threaded enterprise servers, utilization is not a good proxy for
 275 power for arbitrary workloads.

276 Enterprise servers come with automatic temperature-driven
 277 variable fan control policies. When fan speed changes, so does
 278 the airflow and the server cooling capacity [22]. Our method-
 279 ology also considers the contribution of variable fan speed, al-
 280 lowing us to predict temperature in heterogeneous data center
 281 setups running arbitrary workloads.

282 At the server level, Heather et al. [23] propose a server
 283 temperature prediction model based on simplified thermody-
 284 namic equations obtaining results within 1°C of accuracy. Even
 285 though this approach predicts CPU temperature and takes into
 286 account inlet temperature, it does not predict the inlet and needs
 287 specific knowledge about several server parameters. Our ap-
 288 proach only uses data from the generic sensors deployed in the
 289 server and data room.

290 Another common approach to CPU temperature modeling is
 291 the usage of autoregressive moving average (ARMA) model-
 292 ing to estimate future temperature accurately based on previous
 293 measurements [24]. Their main drawbacks are that, because
 294 they only use past temperature samples, the prediction horizon
 295 is usually below one second. Moreover, they do not provide a
 296 physical model, disregarding the effect of power or airflow, and
 297 need to be retrained often.

298 As opposed to others, our work achieves prediction horizons
 299 of 1 minute for CPU temperature and 10 minutes for inlet tem-
 300 perature with high accuracy. This enables data center opera-
 301 tions to take action before thermal events occur, by changing
 302 either the workload or the cooling in the data center.

303 4. Gramatical evolution techniques

304 Evolutionary algorithms use the principles of evolution to
 305 turn one population of solutions into another, by means of selec-
 306 tion, crossover and mutation. Among them, Genetic Program-
 307 ming (GP) has proven to be effective in a number of Symbolic
 308 Regression (SR) problems [25]. However, GP presents some
 309 limitations like bloating of the evolution (excessive growth of
 310 memory computer structures), often produced in the phenotype
 311 of the individual. In the last years, variants to GP like Gram-
 312 matical Evolution (GE) appeared as a simpler optimization pro-
 313 cess [26]. GE is inspired in the biological process of generating
 314 a protein given the DNA of an organism. GE evolves computer
 315 programs given a set of rules, adopting a bio-inspired genotype-
 316 phenotype mapping process.

Figure 2: CPU temperature prediction diagram.

In this section, we describe how we perform feature selec- 317
 318 tion, provide a brief insight on the grammars and mapping pro-
 319 cess, as well as on several model parameters.

320 4.1. Feature selection and model definition

321 In this work we use Feature Engineering (FE) and Grammat-
 322 ical Evolution to obtain a mathematical expression that models
 323 CPU and server inlet temperature. This expression is derived
 324 from experimental measurements in real server and data room
 325 scenarios, gathering data that have an impact on temperature,
 326 according to previous work in the area [12, 18]. To predict CPU
 327 temperature, we gather server power, fan speed, inlet tempera-
 328 ture and previous CPU temperature measurements. For inlet
 329 temperature, we gather the CRAC air supply and return tem-
 330 perature, humidity, pressure difference through perforated tiles
 331 (which is a measurement that provides information about air-
 332 flow) and previous inlet temperature measurements. Our goal
 333 is to predict temperature a certain time (samples) in advance,
 334 by using past data of the available magnitudes within a win-
 335 dow. We may use past samples from the magnitude we need to
 336 predict, or even previously predicted data.

337 For illustration purposes, in Figure 2 we show a diagram in
 338 which CPU temperature is predicted 1 minute ahead given: i)
 339 2 minutes of past measurements (data window) for fan speed,
 340 server power, inlet and CPU temperature and, ii) the previous
 341 CPU temperature predictions (prediction window).

342 Formally, we claim that CPU temperature prediction for a
 343 certain time instant α samples into the future is a function of
 344 past data measurements within a window of size $i = \{0..W_{cpu}\}$,
 345 and previously predicted values within a window of size $j =$
 346 $\{1..\alpha\}$ as expressed in Eq.(1):

$$\hat{T}_{CPU}(k + \alpha) = f(T_{inlet}(k - i), FS(k - i), P(k - i), T_{CPU}(k - i), \hat{T}_{CPU}(k + j)) \quad (1)$$

347 where T_{inlet} is a short form for the previous inlet temperature
 348 values in a window: $\{T_{inlet}(k - i) | i \in \{0, \dots, W_{cpu}\}\}$. T_{CPU} , FS 349

349 and P are past CPU temperature, fan speed, and server power
 350 consumption values respectively, which are defined similarly,
 351 and \widehat{T}_{CPU} are previous temperature predictions.

352 For inlet temperature, our claim is that inlet temperature T_{inlet}
 353 of a certain server is driven by the room thermal dynamics and
 354 can be expressed as a function of the cold air supply (or return)
 355 temperature, T_{CRAC} , differential pressure across perforated tiles
 356 γ (measured in inches of water, inH_2O) and data room humidity
 357 h (in percentage), as in Eq.(2):

$$\widehat{T}_{inlet}(k + \beta) = f(T_{CRAC}(k - i), \gamma(k - i), h(k - i), \quad (2)$$

$$FS_{p-m}(k - i), \widehat{T}_{inlet}(k + j))$$

358 where the data window can be defined in the range $i = \{0..W_{inlet}\}$
 359 and the prediction window is $j = \{1..\beta\}$

360 Note that, in general, α and β are not equal, as the room dy-
 361 namics are much slower than the CPU temperature dynamics
 362 of the servers, i.e. in a real data room we might need hours
 363 to appreciate substantial differences in ambient temperature,
 364 whereas CPU temperature changes within seconds. The selec-
 365 tion of relevant features among all data measurements is a Sym-
 366 bolic Regression (SR) problem. In our approach, GE allows the
 367 generation of mathematical models applying SR.

368 Regarding both the structure and the internal operators, GE
 369 works like a classic Genetic Algorithm [27]. GE evolves a pop-
 370 ulation formed by a set of individuals, each one constituted by a
 371 chromosome and a fitness value. In SR, the fitness value is usu-
 372 ally a regression metric like Mean Squared Error (MSE). In GE,
 373 a chromosome is a string of integers. In the optimization pro-
 374 cess, GA operators, are iteratively applied to improve the fitness
 375 value of each individual. In order to compute the fitness func-
 376 tion for every iteration and extract the mathematical expression
 377 given by an individual (phenotype), a mapping process is ap-
 378 plied to the chromosome (genotype). This mapping process is
 379 achieved by defining a set of rules to obtain the mathematical
 380 expression, using grammars in Backus Naur Form (BNF) [26].

381 The process does not only perform parameter identification.
 382 In conjunction with a well-defined fitness function, the evolu-
 383 tionary algorithm is also computing mathematical expressions
 384 with the set of features that best fit the target system. Thus, GE
 385 is also defining the optimal set of features that derive into the
 386 most accurate power model.

387 Moreover, this methodology can be used to predict magni-
 388 tudes with memory, such as temperature, where the current ob-
 389 servation depends on past values. To incorporate time depen-
 390 dence, data used for model creation needs to be a timeseries. In
 391 addition, we need to tune our grammars so that they can pro-
 392 duce models where past temperature values can be used to pre-
 393 dict temperature a certain number of samples into the future.
 394 Grammar 1 shows an example where variable x may take val-
 395 ues in the current time step k , i.e., $x[k-0]$ or in previous sam-
 396 ples like $x[k-1]$ or $x[k-2]$. Moreover, a new variable $xpred[k-idx]$
 397 can be included, that accounts for previously predicted values
 398 of variable x .

399 Including time dependence into a grammar has some draw-
 400 backs. First, we are substantially increasing the search space

of our algorithms, as now the GE needs to search for the best
 solution among all variables within the specified window. As
 a consequence, the number of generations needed to obtain a
 good fitness value increases. Second, as we show in the re-
 sults section, depending on the prediction horizon the models
 tend to fall into a local optimum, in which the best phenotype is
 the last available observation of the predicted variable. To ad-
 dress the latter challenge, we propose the use of the premature
 convergence prevention techniques that are next explained, and
 that also benefit the converge time of our algorithms. Despite
 the drawbacks, introducing time dependence in our modeling
 is a must, as temperature transients (both at the server and the
 data center level) are not negligible and need to be accurately
 predicted.

For a more detailed explanation on the principles of the map-
 ping process, and how the BNF grammars are used to incorpo-
 rate time dependence, the reader is referred to the Appendix.

Grammar 1 Example of a grammar in BNF that generates phe-
 notypes with time dependence

$\langle expr \rangle ::= \langle expr \rangle \langle op \rangle \langle expr \rangle \mid \langle preop \rangle (\langle expr \rangle) \mid \langle var \rangle$ (I)

$\langle op \rangle ::= + \mid - \mid * \mid /$ (II)

$\langle preop \rangle ::= \sin \mid \cos \mid \log$ (III)

$\langle var \rangle ::= x[k-\langle idx \rangle] \mid xpred[k-\langle idx \rangle] \mid y \mid z \mid \langle num \rangle$ (IV)

$\langle num \rangle ::= \langle dig \rangle . \langle dig \rangle \mid \langle dig \rangle$ (V)

$\langle dig \rangle ::= 0 \mid 1 \mid 2 \mid 3 \mid 4 \mid 5$ (VI)

$\langle idx \rangle ::= 0 \mid 1 \mid 2$ (VII)

4.2. Preventing premature convergence

Premature convergence of a genetic algorithm arises when
 the chromosomes of some high rated individuals quickly domi-
 nate the population, reducing diversity, and constraining it to
 converge to a local optimum. Premature convergence is one of
 the major shortcomings when trying to model low variability
 magnitudes by using GE techniques.

To overcome the lack of variety in the population, work by
 Kureichick et al. [28] proposes the usage of Social Disaster
 Techniques (SDT). This technique is based on monitoring the
 population to find local optima, and apply an operator:

1. *Packing*: all individuals having the same fitness value ex-
 cept one are fully randomized.
2. *Judgment day*: only the fittest individual survives while
 the remaining are fully randomized.

Work by Rocha et al. [29] proposes the usage of Random
 Off-spring Generation (ROG) to prevent the crossover of two
 individuals with equal genotype, as this would result in the off-
 spring being equal to the parents. Individuals are tested before
 crossover and, if equal, then one off-spring (1-RO) or both of
 them (2-RO) are randomly generated.

Both previous solutions have shown important benefits in classical Genetic Algorithms problems. In our work, we use these techniques to improve the convergence time of our solutions, as we show in Section 6.

4.3. Fitness

The goal of using GE for data room thermal modeling is to obtain accurate models. Thus, our fitness function needs to express the error resulting in the estimation process. To measure the accuracy in our prediction, we would preferably use the Mean Absolute Error (MAE). However, because temperature is a magnitude that varies slowly and might remain constant during large time intervals, we need to give higher weight to large errors. To this end, the fitness function f presented in Eq.(3) tries to reduce the variance of the model, leading the evolution to obtain solutions that minimize the the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE):

$$f = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \cdot \sum_i e_i^2} \quad (3)$$

where the estimation error e_i represents the deviation between the real temperature samples (both for CPU and inlet temperature modeling) obtained by the monitoring system T , and the estimation obtained by the model \hat{T} . i represents each sample of the entire set of N samples used to train the algorithms.

4.4. Problem constraints

As we are modeling the behavior of physical magnitudes for optimization purposes, we need to obtain a solution with physical meaning. To this end, we constrain the general problem of temperature modeling in several ways that are subsequently presented, while still being able to address heterogeneous workloads, architectures and topologies. In the results section we evaluate the impact of these constraints on the model generation stage.

4.4.1. Constraining the grammar

The mathematical expressions can be constrained to a limited number of functions with physical meaning. Because temperature exhibits exponential transients, we can include the exponential function in our grammar, whereas we do not find physical basis to include other mathematical functions such as sines or cosines.

4.4.2. Fitness biasing

Some parameters drive the variables being modeled. For instance, power consumption drives CPU temperature. As we want to obtain models able to capture the physical phenomena that drive temperature, this magnitude should be present in the final model. Thus, CPU temperature models that do not include power in their phenotype are expected to provide good results in the training phase, but to perform poorly for the test, as they are not capturing the physical phenomena. To solve this issue, we can force the appearance of some parameters by biasing the fitness, giving higher weights (i.e. worse fitness) to expressions

that miss a parameter. By biasing fitness we speed-up convergence, we ensure that our models incorporate all parameters directly correlated with temperature, but we could obtain less accurate results.

4.4.3. Real vs. mixed models

Purely real models only use real temperature data measurements to predict future samples. Purely predictive models do not use previous temperature measurements, but may use previous predictions. Mixed models may use both real and predicted data. Adding the predicted samples as a variable increases the size of the search space but may provide higher accuracy.

5. Experimental Methodology

In this section we describe the experimental methodology followed in this paper to model server and environmental parameters in Data Centers. First, we describe an scenario consisting only in the temperature prediction of one server in a small air-cooled data room. We use this scenario to tune the model parameters, testing those that generate better models and studying the convergence of the solutions. Then, we apply the best algorithm configuration to a real data center. As a case study, we use real traces of CeSViMa Data Center, a High Performance Computing cluster at Universidad Politécnic de Madrid in Spain.

5.1. Reduced scenario

This scenario consists on an Intel Xeon RX-300 S6 server equipped with 1 quad-core CPU and 16GB of RAM. The server is installed in a rack with another 4 servers, 2 switches and 2 UPS units, in an air-cooled data room of approximately $30m^2$, with the rack inlet facing the cold air supply and the outlet to the heat exhaust. The cooling infrastructure consists on a Daikin FTXS30 split that pumps cold air from the ceiling, and there is no floor plenum. The cold air supply ranges from $16^\circ C$ to $26^\circ C$. The data room is fully monitored, and both the cooling and server workload are controllable.

5.1.1. Monitoring

Both the server and data room are fully monitored using the internal server sensors and a wireless sensor network, as described in [18]. In particular, server CPU temperature and fan speed values are obtained via the server internal sensors, collected through the Intelligent Platform Management Interface (IPMI) tool ¹. IPMI allows polling the internal sensors of enterprise servers with negligible overhead. As the server is not shipped with power consumption sensors, we use non-intrusive current clamps connected to the power cord of the server to gather total server power consumption. Wireless sensors monitor the inlet temperature of the server, the cold air supply temperature of the split unit and data room humidity. Data are sent to the monitoring server, stored and aligned to ensure a common timestamp.

¹<http://ipmitool.sourceforge.net/>

Figure 3: Training samples used for CPU temperature modeling

Figure 4: CeSViMa data room layout. Models are developed for Power7 nodes 1,4 and 7 at high c02 in racks 1 and 4.

5.1.2. Training and test set generation

We generate the training and test set by assigning a wide variety of workloads that exhibit various stress levels in the CPU and memory subsystems of the server while we modify the cold air supply temperature of the split in a range from 16°C to 26°C. All workloads used are a representative set, in terms of stress to the server subsystem and power consumption, of the ones that can be found in High-Performance Computing data centers. Also, the temperatures selected for cold air supply temperature are within the allowable ranges in current data centers.

The workloads used are the following: i) *Lookbusy*², a synthetic workload that stresses the CPU to a customizable utilization value, avoiding the stress of memory and disk; ii) a modified version of the synthetic benchmark *RandMem*³, that allows us to stress random memory regions of a given size with a given access pattern, and iii) HPC workloads belonging to the SPEC CPU 2006 benchmark suite [30].

During training, we launch *Lookbusy* and *Randmem* at various utilization values, plus a subset of the SPEC CPU 2006 benchmarks that exhibit a distinctive set of characteristics according to Phansalkar et al. [31]. Both the arrival time and task duration are randomly selected. During execution, the cold air supply temperature is also randomly changed. For the test set, we randomly launch a SPEC CPU benchmark, with random waiting intervals while changing cold air supply temperature.

Our monitoring system collects all data with a 10 second sampling interval for a total time of 5 hours for the training and 10 hours for the test set. Figure 3 shows part of the training set used for modeling.

5.2. Case study: CeSViMa Data Center

To show how our solution can be applied to a real data center scenario, this paper presents a case study for a real High-Performance Computing Data Center at the Madrid Supercomputing and Visualization Center (CeSViMa)⁴. CeSViMa hosts

the *Magerit* Supercomputer, a cluster consisting of 286 computer nodes in 11 racks, providing 4,160 processors to execute High-Performance jobs on demand. 245 of the 286 nodes are IBM PS702 2S with 2 Power7 CPU's blade servers, each with 8 cores running at 3.3GHz and 32GB of RAM. The other 41 nodes are HS22 2U servers with 2 Intel Xeon processors of 8 cores each at 2.5GHz and 64GB RAM.

CeSViMa data room has a cold-hot aisle layout and is cooled by means of 6 CRAC units arranged in the walls that impulse air through the floor plenum. To control data room cooling, the air return temperature of each CRAC unit can be set independently. The room has a total size of 190 square meters. Figure 4a shows the layout of the data center. Rack 0 is a control rack that runs no HPC computation. Racks 1-9 are filled with Power7 blade servers, whereas rack 10 contains Intel Xeon servers. Each Power7 node is installed in a blade center. Each blade center contains up to 7 blades, and each rack contains 4 chassis (C01 to C04), as shown in Figure 4b. To run our models, we have deployed the same sensor network as in the reduced scenario. In particular, to model inlet temperature we gather inlet temperature, humidity, CRAC air return temperature and differential pressure through the floor plenum. Because we have placed pressure sensors in the tiles in front of racks 1 and 4, we model the Power7 nodes in these racks. To model CPU temperature, we also collect CPU temperature and fan speed of all servers via IPMI. CeSViMa Power7 chassis do not have per-server power sensors and we are not able to deploy current clamps. Thus, we use per-server utilization as a proxy for the power consumption of the node. As stated before, utilization is not an accurate metric for arbitrary workloads. However, because of the nature of the workloads in CeSViMa and only for thermal modeling purposes, utilization can be used as a proxy variable to power consumption, as we show in Section 6.

In this work we show the modeling results for the servers highlighted in red in Figure 4, i.e. nodes 1,4,7 at chassis c02 of both rack 1 and 4. These nodes are the ones that exhibit the most variable workload and extreme temperature conditions and constitute the worst-case scenario for modeling.

²<http://www.devin.com/lookbusy/>

³<http://www.roylongbottom.org.uk>

⁴<http://www.cesvima.upm.es/>

5.3. Modeling framework

Because of the large number of servers in CeSViMa, to enable cooling optimization we need a framework that allows to automatically model and predict the CPU and inlet temperature of all servers. Even though CeSViMa is a small-sized data room, it has a very high density in terms of IT equipment. For instance, the amount of data gathered that needs to be processed to enable full environmental modeling and prediction, for a period of 1 year, is above 100GB. Thus, modeling the whole data center with traditional approaches that require human interaction is not feasible.

Our work uses the proposed GE techniques to automatically model all the parameters involved in data center optimization by automatically running the training of the algorithms and testing them during runtime.

6. Results

In this section we present the experimental results obtained when applying Grammatical Evolution to model CPU and inlet temperature. First, we show the results for the controlled scenario, describing the best algorithm configuration, and compare our method with state-of-the-art solutions. Then, we apply the best configuration to train and test the models in a real data center scenario.

6.1. Algorithm setup and performance

First, we use GE to obtain a set of candidate solutions with low error when compared to the temperature measurements in our controlled experimental setup, under different constraints.

After evaluating the performance of our model with several setups, we select the following one for each model in this paper:

- Population size: 200 individuals
- Chromosome length: 100 codons
- Mutation probability: inversely proportional to the number of rules.
- Crossover probability: 0.9
- Maximum wraps: 3
- Codon size: 8 bits (values from 0 to 255)
- Tournament size: 2 (binary)

For CPU temperature prediction, we use a data window of $W_{cpu} = 20$ samples (corresponding to 200 seconds) and a prediction window of $\alpha = 6$ (corresponding to 60 seconds). The data window is heuristically chosen with respect to the largest observed temperature transient, and its size is a trade-off between model accuracy and convergence time. In this sense, the data window needs to incorporate enough samples to capture the trends of thermal transients, but we also need to consider that the larger the data window, the larger the exploration space. The prediction window needs to be selected with respect to the time it takes to actuate on the system and observe a response. In

our case, the data window size W_{cpu} has been chosen in accordance to our previous work on server power modeling, where we analytically modeled temperature transients in enterprise servers, observing that the largest transients, i.e. the worst-case modeling scenario, occur for the lower fan speed values [12]. The prediction window is chosen given the physical constraints of the problem: 1-minute prediction is sufficient time to change the workload assignment of a server, as canceling the workload of a server in case of thermal redlining takes few seconds.

For inlet temperature prediction, we also use a data window of $W_{inlet} = 20$ samples but a prediction window of $\beta = 5$ samples. Inlet temperature dynamics are much slower than CPU temperature. Because of this, a sampling rate of 2 minutes over inlet temperature is sufficient to get accurate results. Given the size of the prediction window, we are able to obtain inlet temperature samples 10 minutes advance, which is sufficient time to act upon data room cooling.

Next, we present the comparison among several configurations in terms of grammar expressions and rules, premature convergence prevention and fitness biasing. We detail our results for CPU temperature modeling. The procedure to tune inlet temperature models is completely equivalent.

6.1.1. Data preprocessing and model simplification

Because the power measurements of the Intel Xeon server are taken with a current clamp, the power values obtained exhibit some noise. We preprocess the data to eliminate high-frequency noise, smoothing the power consumption trace by means of a low pass filter. The remaining traces did not exhibit noise, so no preprocessing was needed.

Moreover, we perform variable standardization for every feature (in the range [1, 2]) to assure the same probability of appearance for all the variables and to enhance the GE symbolic regression.

6.1.2. Grammars used

To model CPU temperature we have tested three different grammars:

- The first is shown in Grammar 2 and contains a wide set of operands and preoperands (rules II and III), that do not necessarily yield models with a physical meaning.
- The second grammar is a variation of Grammar 2 in which the number of preoperands (rule III) is reduced to exponentials only, i.e. $\langle preop \rangle ::= exp$
- The last grammar is the one presented in Grammar 3 and also reduces the set of possible expressions (rule I).

From the previous three grammars the one that has faster convergence time to achieve a low error, is Grammar 3. Constraining the grammar improves convergence time and provides phenotypes that have physical meaning, without an increase in the modeling error obtained. Thus, for the remaining of the paper we work with the simplified Grammar 3 when modeling CPU temperature.

Grammar 2 Grammar used for CPU temperature modeling in BNF, that uses inlet temperature (TIN), fan speed (FS), power consumption (PS), past CPU temperature (TS) and past predicted CPU temperature (TpS)

$$\langle expr \rangle ::= \langle expr \rangle \langle op \rangle \langle expr \rangle | (\langle expr \rangle \langle op \rangle \langle expr \rangle) | \langle preop \rangle (\langle expr \rangle) \langle var \rangle \langle cte \rangle \quad (I)$$

$$\langle op \rangle ::= +|-|*|/ \quad (II)$$

$$\langle preop \rangle ::= \exp | \sin | \cos | \tan \quad (III)$$

$$\langle var \rangle ::= TS[k-\langle idx \rangle] | TIN[k-\langle idx \rangle] | PS[k-\langle idx \rangle] | FS[k-\langle idx \rangle] \quad (IV)$$

$$\langle idx \rangle ::= \langle dgt2 \rangle \langle dgt \rangle \quad (V)$$

$$\langle cte \rangle ::= \langle dgt \rangle . \langle dgt \rangle \quad (VI)$$

$$\langle dgt \rangle ::= 0|1|2|3|4|5|6|7|8|9 \quad (VII)$$

$$\langle dgt2 \rangle ::= 0|1 \quad (VIII)$$

Grammar 3 Simplified grammar in BNF format used for CPU temperature modeling

$$\langle expr \rangle ::= \langle expr \rangle \langle op \rangle \langle expr \rangle | (\langle expr \rangle \langle op \rangle \langle expr \rangle) | \langle preop \rangle (\langle exponent \rangle) \langle var \rangle \langle cte \rangle \quad (I)$$

$$\langle op \rangle ::= +|-|*|/ \quad (II)$$

$$\langle preop \rangle ::= \exp \quad (III)$$

$$\langle exponent \rangle ::= \langle sign \rangle \langle cte \rangle * \langle var \rangle | \langle sign \rangle \langle cte \rangle * (\langle var \rangle \langle op \rangle \langle var \rangle) \quad (IV)$$

$$\langle sign \rangle ::= +|- \quad (V)$$

$$\langle var \rangle ::= TpS[k-\langle idx \rangle] | TS[k-\langle idx \rangle] | TIN[k-\langle idx \rangle] | PS[k-\langle idx \rangle] | FS[k-\langle idx \rangle] \quad (VI)$$

$$\langle idx \rangle ::= \langle dgt \rangle \quad (VII)$$

$$\langle cte \rangle ::= \langle dgt2 \rangle . \langle dgt2 \rangle \quad (VIII)$$

$$\langle dgt \rangle ::= 1|2|3|4|5|6|7|8|9|10|11|12|13|14 | 15|16|17|18|19|20 \quad (IX)$$

$$\langle dgt2 \rangle ::= 0|1|2|3|4|5|6|7|8|9 \quad (X)$$

a) Error evolution with number of generations for real models

b) Error evolution with number of generations for mixed models

Figure 5: CPU temperature error evolution for real and mixed models under different premature convergence prevention techniques: i) no technique applied, ii) ROG + SDT keeping 5% of equal individuals and iii) ROG + SDT randomizing all equal individuals.

We test two variations of this grammar: i) one that searches for a mixed model (i.e. uses past temperature predictions, and it is the one shown in Grammar 3), and ii) the one that provides a real model (i.e. only uses CPU temperature measurements). The only difference between the mixed and the real grammars, is the presence of the parameter TpS .

6.1.3. Tested configurations

With respect to premature convergence, we test three different techniques:

- No premature convergence technique applied
- Random Off-Spring Generation (2-RO) plus Packing, keeping no more that a 5% of equal individuals.
- Random Off-Spring Generation (2-RO) plus Packing, leaving no more than 1 individual with equal phenotype.

For each of the previous configurations, we run both real and mixed models, with the goal of comparing the convergence time and the fitness evolution of each configuration. Because of the random evolution of the algorithms, for comparison purposes, we run the same model training 5 times and average the RMSE obtained for different number of generations. Figure 5 shows the RMSE evolution for the three configurations, with both real and mixed models.

When we do not apply any technique, error decay is much slower, as population loses diversity and improves only due to mutation in the individuals. The impact is higher for the mixed models, where search space is larger. When we apply ROG and SDT, we need less generations to obtain good fitness values. However, keeping only 1 individual with the same phenotype and randomizing the remaining population is too aggressive,

Figure 6: CPU temperature error evolution for real and mixed models under ROG + SDT 5% when fitness is biased vs. not biased.

while keeping a higher percentage of equal individuals, i.e. a 5%, yields better results. As shown, using 30,000 generations is enough to obtain low RMSE values.

Regarding fitness biasing, Figure 6 shows the differences in terms of RMSE for different number of generations for real and mixed models when we bias the fitness to force all parameters and when we do not bias it. Convergence is similar, being slightly better that of the non-biased models. In fact, all variables in the grammar tend to appear in non-biased models, backing up the hypothesis that all those magnitudes are correlated with temperature.

Finally, we show results for both the training and test set when modeling CPU temperature with the best configuration, i.e. a mixed model obtained with Grammar 3, using ROG and Packing techniques leaving 5% of equal individuals, and not biasing the fitness. Table 1 shows the 5 better phenotypes obtained and their corresponding RMSE and MAE values for the test set after simplification. To avoid overfitting, we use the five best models to compute the samples of the test set, i.e., we predict the next temperature sample with all five equations, obtaining 5 different results, and we average them to obtain the prediction value. By applying this methodology we obtain a RMSE of 2.48°C and a MAE of 1.77°C. Because CPU temperature sensors usually have a resolution of 1°C we consider these results to be accurate enough for our purposes. Figure 7 shows a zoom-in of the real CPU temperature trace and its prediction, for both the training and the test set. As can be seen, the prediction accurately matches the measured values in both the training and test sets.

6.2. Comparison to other approaches

We compare our results with three common techniques for CPU temperature modeling in the state-of-the-art: autoregressive moving average models, linear subspace identification techniques and dynamic neural networks. We first briefly describe these three modeling techniques and then we show the results obtained and compare them with our proposed technique.

6.2.1. ARMA models

ARMA models are mathematical models of autocorrelation in a time series, that use past values alone to forecast future values of a magnitude. ARMA models assume the underlying model as stationary and that there is a serial correlation with the data, something that temperature modeling accomplishes. In a

(a) 1-minute training set prediction for mixed model

(b) 1-minute test set prediction for mixed model

Figure 7: Training and test set CPU temperature prediction vs. real measurements with time (secs)

general way, an ARMA model can be described as in Equation 4:

$$y_t = \sum_{i=1}^p (a_i \cdot y_{t-i}) = e_t + \sum_{j=1}^q (c_j \cdot e_{t-j}) \quad (4)$$

where y_t is the value of the time series (CPU temperature in our case) at time t , a_i 's are the lag- i autoregressive coefficients, c_j 's are the moving average coefficient and e_t is the error. The error is assumed to be random and normally distributed. p and q are the orders of the autoregressive (AR) and the moving average (MA) parts of the model, respectively.

The ARMA modeling methodology consists on two different steps: i) identification and ii) estimation. In our work we use an automated methodology similar to the one proposed by Coskun et.al. [24]. During the identification phase, the model order is computed, i.e. we find the optimum values for p and q of the $ARMA(p, q)$ process. To perform model identification we use an automated strategy, that computes the goodness of fit for a range of p and q values, starting by the simplest model (i.e., an $ARMA(1,0)$). The goodness of fit is computed using the Final Prediction Error (FPE), and the best model is the one with lowest FPE value, given by Equation 5:

$$FPE = \frac{1 + n/N}{1 - n/N} \cdot V \quad (5)$$

where $n = p + q$, N is the length of the time series and V is the variance of the model residuals. For a fair comparison with our proposed methodology, the model obtained needs to forecast $\alpha = 6$ samples.

6.2.2. N4SID

N4SID is a subspace identification method that estimates an n order state-space model using measured input-output data, to obtain a model that represents the following system:

$$\dot{x}(t) = Ax(t) + Bu(t) + Ke(t) \quad (6)$$

$$y(t) = Cx(t) + Du(t) + e(t) \quad (7)$$

Phenotype	RMSE	MAE
$TS[k-3] + PS[k-1] - PS[k-4] + 1.1 \cdot TIN[k-7]/(e^{(-0.1 \cdot (TpS[k-8] - TS[k-3]))} \cdot (PS[k-20]/9.9) + 9.9) - (e^{(-4.5 \cdot (TpS[k-5]/TS[k-19]))} \cdot TS[k-7]) - 9.6$	2.8	2.08
$TS[k-5] + PS[k-1] - PS[k-5] + (TS[k-5]/5.7 - e^{(-1.3 \cdot (TS[k-5]/TIN[k-12]))} \cdot TS[k-5]) + PS[k-11]/(3.7 - TS[k-5]) \cdot (e^{(-0.3 \cdot (PS[k-18] + FS[k-7]))} - e^{(-4.9 \cdot (PS[k-12]/PS[k-16]))}) - 9.8$	2.59	1.86
$TS[k-5] + PS[k-1] - PS[k-4] + e^{(+6.1 \cdot (TIN[k-10]/TS[k-5]))} - 5.2) - TIN[k-14] \cdot (0.06 \cdot (TIN[k-7]/TS[k-5])) + (PS[k-1]/3.1 \cdot TIN[k-7]) \cdot TS[k-5] - (PS[k-20]/TIN[k-7]) \cdot (-6.4 \cdot (TIN[k-15]/TS[k-11])) - 8.0$	2.77	2.01
$TS[k-3] + PS[k-1] - PS[k-4] - e^{(-4.1 \cdot (TpS[k-5]/TIN[k-19]))} / TS[k-3] + (TpS[k-1]/(e^{(-0.1 \cdot (TpS[k-8] - TS[k-3]))} \cdot (PS[k-20]/9.9) + 9.2)))/1.6 - 9.6$	2.55	1.77
$TS[k-1] + 0.73 \cdot (PS[k-1] \cdot 4.4 - PS[k-2] \cdot 4.4 - TS[k-1] + TpS[k-8] + e^{(-0.2 \cdot TIN[k-8])} + (e^{(-3.4 \cdot (PS[k-20]/PS[k-10]))} - e^{(-4.0 \cdot (PS[k-6]/PS[k-19]))}) \cdot TpS[k-12]/9.0 - 0.9)$	2.5	1.75

Table 1: Phenotype, RMSE and MAE for the test set in the CPU temperature modeling reduced scenario

where A, B, C and D are state-space matrices, K is the disturbance matrix, $u(t)$ is the input, $y(t)$ is the output, $x(t)$ is the vector of n states and $e(t)$ is the disturbance.

State-space models are models that use state variable observations to describe a system by a set of first-order differential equations, using a black-box approach. The approach consists on identifying a parameterization of the model, and then determining the parameters so that the measurements explain the model in the most accurate possible way. They have been very successful for the identification of linear multivariable dynamic systems.

To be constructed, certain parameters need to be fed into the model, such as the number of forward predictions (r), the number of past inputs (s_u), and the number of past outputs (s_y). Again, for a fair comparison with our proposed methodology, we need a model in the form $N4SID[r, s_u, s_y]$ where $r = 6$, $s_u = 20$ and $s_y = 20$.

6.2.3. NARX

A Nonlinear Autoregressive eXogenous (NARX) model is a nonlinear autoregressive model with exogenous inputs. In this case, the current value of a time series is computed in function of a) past values of the same series, and b) current and past values of the exogenous series. Additionally, the model contains an error term, since knowledge of the other terms will not enable the current value of the time series to be predicted with precision. This model is described as follows:

$$y(t) = F(y(t-1), y(t-2), y(t-3), \dots, u(t), u(t-1), u(t-2), u(t-3), \dots) + e(t) \quad (8)$$

where $y(t)$ is the output, $u(t)$ is the exogenous variable and $e(t)$ is the error term. F is a nonlinear function, and in our case is defined through a neural network. The NARX model is based on the linear ARX model, which is commonly used in time-series modeling.

6.2.4. Model comparison

Finally, we compare the results for CPU temperature modeling between our proposed approach, ARMA, N4SID, and NARX models, all of them with a prediction window of 6 samples (1 minute). To perform a statistical comparison, we have

Model	Training set		Test set	
	RMSE	MAE	RMSE	MAE
ARMA _{1,4}	3.38 ± 0.23	1.62 ± 0.13	3.23 ± 1.02	1.62 ± 0.57
ARMA _{9,8}	3.35 ± 0.24	1.70 ± 0.14	3.24 ± 1.01	1.74 ± 0.64
N4SID	2.55 ± 0.28	1.69 ± 0.07	3.98 ± 1.11	2.93 ± 0.58
NARX	2.53 ± 0.10	1.64 ± 0.05	3.88 ± 1.16	2.35 ± 0.69
GE	2.32 ± 0.19	1.50 ± 0.08	2.56 ± 0.90	1.66 ± 0.45

Table 2: RMSE and MAE in CPU temperature prediction for each model (ARMA, N4SID, NARX and GE)

Figure 8: Zoomed-in averaged CPU temperature modeling comparison between ARMA(1,4), N4SID, NARX and GE

conducted a non-exhaustive 5-fold cross-validation. The complete data set is obtained from more than 10 hours of temperature traces gathered from an Intel Xeon RX-300 S6 server running a wide range of workloads under various cooling setups. This data set has been partitioned into 5 equal sized subsamples. A single subsample is retained as the validation data for testing the model, and the remaining 4 subsets are used as training data. This process is repeated 5 times with each of the 5 subsamples used exactly once as the validation data. RMSE and MAE are averaged to perform a comparison between ARMA, N4SID, NARX and GE. Each resultant set of five models will be averaged to produce the final estimation.

Table 2 shows the RMSE and MAE errors obtained for our proposed modeling technique based on GE, ARMA, N4SID and NARX models, and Figure 8 shows a zoom-in into the

Figure 9: 10-minute inlet temperature prediction in the reduced scenario for a mixed model with SDT Packing 5% and simplified grammar

Figure 10: Inlet temperature modeling for various racks

857 CPU temperature curve for the actual measurements and the
 858 averaged prediction of the five models obtained in the cross
 859 validation over the whole data set. As can be seen, GE mod-
 860 els are the ones with both lower RMSE and MAE. Moreover,
 861 the CPU temperature trend is accurately predicted. This does
 862 not happen for ARMA models that, even though keep the max-
 863 imum error low, provide values that are always behind the real
 864 trend, yielding poor forecasting capabilities. This issue cannot
 865 be solved by increasing the model order, as shown in Table 2.
 866 N4SID models, even though they are very accurate in the train-
 867 ing set, perform poorly in the test set and have an important
 868 bias error. Even if the bias error is corrected (which has been
 869 done in Figure 8) the prediction is still behind the measure-
 870 ments and the model is unable to capture the system dynamics.
 871 NARX models clearly show an overfitting effect in the train-
 872 ing data. The GE prediction, even though has more oscillations
 873 (due to the smoothed noise of the power consumption signal) is
 874 the only one that captures the temperature trend, advancing the
 875 real measurements.

876 6.3. Inlet temperature modeling

877 For inlet temperature modeling we perform the same study
 878 than for CPU temperature in terms of grammars, premature
 879 convergence and fitness biasing. As expected, the results in
 880 terms of the best model configuration yield very similar results.
 881 Thus, for inlet temperature modeling, we use the same configu-
 882 ration: i) a mixed model using a simplified version of the gram-
 883 mar that only allows exponentials, ii) SDT with 5% packing
 884 and iii) RMSE fitness function without biasing.

885 The BNF grammar used is very similar to Grammar 3, where
 886 instead of rule VI, we use the following rule:

$$\langle var \rangle ::= \text{TIN}[k-\langle idx \rangle] \mid \text{TpIN}[k-\langle idx \rangle] \\ \mid \text{TSUP}[k-\langle idx \rangle] \mid \text{HUM}[k-\langle idx \rangle]$$

887 where TSUP is cold air supply temperature, HUM is humidity,
 888 TIN are past inlet temperatures and TpIN are past inlet temper-
 889 ature predictions. Figure 9 shows the prediction for the test
 890 set. The RMSE of the prediction is of 0.33°C and MAE is
 891 0.27°C for a prediction window of 10 minutes and for the test
 892 set. Again, the model includes all the available variables, i.e.,
 893 TSUP, TIN and HUM appear in the final model.

894 6.4. Data Center modeling

895 We use the previous model with the same configuration to
 896 predict the CPU and inlet temperature of the blade servers at

897 CeSViMa data center. Because CeSViMa is a production en-
 898 vironment, when it comes to server data, we are subject to the
 899 data sampling rates provided by the data center. CeSViMa col-
 900 lects all data from servers every 2 minutes, and environmen-
 901 tal data (i.e. from coolers) every 15 minutes. Thus, for both
 902 CPU and inlet temperatures, we need to change our prediction
 903 windows. For CPU temperature we use a prediction window
 904 $\alpha' = 1$, which means that we predict CPU temperature
 905 two minutes into the future. For inlet temperature we use a predic-
 906 tion window $\beta' = 1$ samples, i.e. we predict temperature 15
 907 minutes ahead.

908 Because in CeSViMa we cannot control the workload being
 909 executed, nor modify the cooling setup, we need to select longer
 910 training and tests sets to ensure that they exhibit high variability
 911 on the magnitudes of interest. For CPU temperature, we select 2
 912 days of execution for the training set, and 4 days for the test set.
 913 For inlet temperature, which varies very slowly in a real data
 914 center setup we use 14 days of execution for both the training
 915 and the test set.

916 Figure 10 shows a zoomed-in plot of the measured and pre-
 917 dicted inlet temperature to the chassis c02 of racks 1 and 4 in
 918 CeSViMa data center for a period of 8 days. Figure 11 shows
 919 the measured and predicted CPU temperature traces for blades
 920 b01, b04 and b07 in chassis c02 of both racks, for the first two
 921 days of the same period, as well as the prediction error (i.e. the
 922 difference between the real measurements and the prediction).
 923 To generate these last models, instead of using the real inlet
 924 temperature measurements, we use predicted inlet temperature.
 925 This way, we are able to accurately predict all variables needed
 926 for optimization.

927 Table 3 shows the phenotypes obtained for CPU and temper-
 928 ature modeling of the servers in CeSViMa data center. We also
 929 report MAE for both training and test sets. We observe that
 930 all phenotypes that model CPU temperature incorporate the pa-
 931 rameters of interest (inlet temperature, power and fan speed),
 932 and we obtain errors below 1°C in all cases. The average RMSE
 933 across models are 1.52°C and 1.57°C for the training and test
 934 set respectively. As for inlet temperature, the phenotypes in-
 935 corporate both differential pressure, and CRAC return tempera-
 936 ture. Moreover, depending on the rack placement, the influ-
 937 ence of the CRAC units vary. Here we can observe the benefits
 938 of the feature selection performed by GE. Rack1, which is the
 939 leftmost rack in the data center, is affected only by CRAC2;
 940 whereas Rack4, situated in the middle of the row, is affected

Figure 11: Data Center CPU temperature modeling and prediction error for various servers in different racks for 2 days of traces (time in hours)

941 both by CRAC2 and CRAC3. The model automatically incor- 964
 942 porates the most relevant features, discarding the irrelevant 965
 943 ones. For inlet temperature prediction, our error is below 0.5°C, 966
 944 which is enough for our purposes and below other state-of-the- 967
 945 art approaches. 968

946 7. Discussion 969

947 In this section we briefly discuss the applicability of our mod- 970
 948 els, and the computational effort needed to model a full data 971
 949 center scenario, to validate the feasibility of our approach. 972

950 7.1. Applicability 973

951 The goal of our modeling is predicting server CPU temper- 974
 952 ature under variable cooling setups, so that cooling-associated 975
 953 costs can be reduced without incurring on reliability issues. To 976
 954 this end, we first predict the inlet temperature of servers given 977
 955 the data room conditions and cooling setup, and use this result 978
 956 to predict server temperature. 979

957 Having analyzed the spatio-temporal variability of inlet tem- 980
 958 perature traces in CeSViMa data center, we find that it is suf- 981
 959 ficient to predict inlet temperature at 3 different heights (at the 982
 960 bottom, middle and top of the rack), in one out of two racks. 983
 961 This way, we need to generate 30 inlet temperature models at 984
 962 most. Because the maximum CPU temperature in the data center 985
 963 is the one limiting the cooling, at most we need to predict 986

the CPU temperature of each server in the data room, i.e. we 964
 need as many models as servers in the data center. However, if 965
 by analyzing the traces we find that there is a subset of CPUs 966
 that limit the maximum cooling of the overall data center, our 967
 problem can be reduced to modeling those that always exhibit 968
 higher temperatures. For the particular case of the traces of 969
 CeSViMa, if we examine 6 months of CPU temperature traces, 970
 we find that the CPUs limiting the cooling are the blades b04 971
 and b07 placed in the second chassis (c02) of all racks. In this 972
 sense, for energy optimization purposes our problem reduces to 973
 generating 10 different models. These models allow us to pre- 974
 dict the maximum server temperature attained in the data center 975
 and, thus, detect any potential thermal redlining and act before 976
 it occurs. Moreover, to leverage energy optimization, our re- 977
 sults can be used to set cooling dynamically during runtime, 978
 by predicting the maximum data center CPU temperature un- 979
 der various cooling conditions and increasing CRAC air supply 980
 temperature without incurring in reliability issues. 981

Even though in this paper we have applied our modeling 982
 methodology to a raised-floor air-cooled data center scenario, 983
 the proposed technique is also valid for data centers equipped 984
 with other state-of-the-art cooling mechanisms, such as in-row 985
 or in-rack cooling used in high-density racks. 986

987 7.2. Computational effort 990

Our approach is computationally intensive in the model train- 988
 ing stage. The GE model needs to evolve a random initial pop- 989

Model	Phenotype	Train.	Test
Inlet Rack1	$TIN[k-1] + e^{(-4.3 \cdot (TRET2[k-3]/TRET2[k-11]))} / TIN[k-1] \cdot (e^{(+1.5 \cdot TIN[k-5])} - e^{(-3.8 \cdot (PDIF[k-20] - TIN[k-1]))})$	0.32	0.4
Inlet Rack4	$TIN[k-1] + 3.1 / e^{(+5.0 \cdot TIN[k-1])} \cdot e^{(+2.2 \cdot TIN[k-2])} - e^{(-2.9 \cdot TpIN[k-3])} \cdot TRET3[k-12] \cdot (TRET3[k-5] + e^{(-4.9 \cdot (HUM[k-6]/TRET2[k-1]))} / TIN[k-2] / e^{(+7.2 \cdot (PDIF[k-20] - TIN[k-1]))})$	0.18	0.44
CPU Rack1, C02, B01	$TS[k-1] + (PS[k-20] \cdot FS[k-1] - 9.4 \cdot (TpS[k-5] \cdot TpS[k-2])) / (e^{(+2.0 \cdot FS[k-7])} / e^{(-4.1 \cdot TpS[k-5])} / (2.3 + e^{(+1.7 \cdot (TpS[k-10] \cdot TpS[k-10]))} + e^{(+1.5 \cdot FS[k-1])} - e^{(+1.6 \cdot PS[k-7]))})$	0.68	0.76
CPU Rack1, C02, B04	$TS[k-1] + e^{(-7.2 \cdot (TS[k-6]/PS[k-1]))} / (e^{(-6.1 \cdot (TS[k-10] - PS[k-15]))} / 5.6 / FS[k-20] - 1.7 + TpS[k-20] - e^{(-3.0 \cdot (TIN[k-4]/TS[k-15]))})$		
CPU Rack1, C02, B07	$TS[k-1] + e^{(-6.2 \cdot (TS[k-2] \cdot TIN[k-11]))} / ((e^{(-9.8 \cdot TS[k-8])} + e^{(-5.2 \cdot (TS[k-9] \cdot PS[k-19]))}) \cdot e^{(+5.8 \cdot FS[k-9]))}$	0.51	0.85
CPU Rack4, C02, B01	$TS[k-1] + e^{(-3.1 \cdot TS[k-2])} / (((TS[k-3]/PS[k-3]) + (FS[k-18] - FS[k-8]) / e^{(-9.4 \cdot (FS[k-1] - TpS[k-9]))}) - TpS[k-4] + (TpS[k-6] + TS[k-3]) - (TIN[k-3]/TpS[k-9]))$	0.55 0.29	0.75 0.46
CPU Rack4, C02, B04	$TS[k-1] + e^{(-5.7 \cdot (TpS[k-6] \cdot TpS[k-10]))} / e^{(+9.9 \cdot (TpS[k-9] - TIN[k-10]))}$	0.26	0.73
CPU Rack4, C02, B07	$TS[k-1] + TIN[k-11] \cdot e^{(-9.5 \cdot (TpS[k-10]/TIN[k-5]))} / e^{(-9.9 \cdot (TIN[k-10] - TS[k-5]))}$	0.43	0.87

Table 3: Phenotype and average error (in Celsius) in training and test set for CPU and inlet temperature modeling in a production Data Center

ulation for 30,000 generations to obtain accurate results. In our experiments, running 30,000 generations of 4 different models in parallel takes 28h in a computer equipped with a QuadCore Intel i7 CPU @3.4GHz and 8GB of RAM. This computational cost is much larger than the computational cost for training ARMA and N4SID models. However, to obtain accurate results ARMA needs to be manually tuned, and N4SID requires a manual feature selection step that greatly impacts accuracy, whereas GE models can be automatically developed.

However, as the models obtained for homogeneous servers are very similar, it is possible to reduce the training overhead by using already evolved populations to fine-tune the models instead of using the a new random population every time. This way, we can reduce the training time significantly.

As for the model testing, in the worst case scenario, the model needs to be tested every 10 seconds. The overhead to test one model is found to be negligible. In this sense, it is feasible to compute all temperatures to find the maximum. Moreover, because of the temperature imbalances of servers in the data room we can reduce the amount of models run to those that are limiting the cooling, i.e. the servers with higher CPU temperature values. Overhead incurred by testing is in the same order of magnitude than the overhead of ARMA and N4SID, but provides better results in terms of error.

8. Conclusions

In this paper we have presented a methodology for the unsupervised generation of models to predict on runtime the thermal behavior of production data centers running arbitrary workloads and equipped with heterogeneous servers.

Our approach leverages the usage of Grammatical Evolution to automatically generate models of the data room by using real data center traces. Our solution allows to predict the CPU temperature and inlet temperature of servers, with an average error below 2°C and 0.5°C respectively. These errors are within the

margin obtained by other off-line supervised approaches in the state-of-the art. Our solution, generates the models in an unsupervised way, is able to work on runtime, is trained and tested in a real scenario, and does not require the usage of CFD software.

To the best of our knowledge our work is the first to propose data center temperature forecasting using evolutionary techniques, allowing predictive model generation for runtime optimization.

Appendix

In this Appendix we provide further information on the mapping process used by our grammar. For a more detailed explanation on the principles of GE, the reader is referred to [32]. A BNF specification is a set of derivation rules, expressed in the form:

$$\langle symbol \rangle ::= \langle expression \rangle$$

Rules are composed of sequences of terminals, which are items that can appear in the language, and non-terminals, which can be expanded into one or more terminals and non-terminals. A grammar is represented by the tuple N, T, P, S , being N the non-terminal set, T is the terminal set, P the production rules for the assignment of elements on N and T , and S is a start symbol that should appear in N . The options within a production rule are separated by a “|” symbol.

Grammar 4 represents an example grammar in BNF. The final expression consists of elements of the set of terminals T , which have been combined with the rules of the grammar.

The chromosome is used to map the start symbol onto terminals by reading genes (or codons) of 8 bits to generate a corresponding integer value, from which the options of a production rule are selected by using the modulus operator:

$$\text{Rule} = \text{Codon Value \% Number of Rule Choices} \quad (9)$$

Grammar 4 Example of a grammar in BNF designed for symbolic regression

$N = \{\text{expr, op, preop, var, num, dig}\}$
 $T = \{+, -, *, /, \sin, \cos, \exp, x, y, z, 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, (,), .\}$
 $S = \{\text{expr}\}$
 $P = \{\text{I, II, III, IV, V, VI}\}$

$\langle \text{expr} \rangle ::= \langle \text{expr} \rangle \langle \text{op} \rangle \langle \text{expr} \rangle \mid \langle \text{preop} \rangle (\langle \text{expr} \rangle) \mid \langle \text{var} \rangle$ (I)

$\langle \text{op} \rangle ::= +|-|*|/$ (II)

$\langle \text{preop} \rangle ::= \sin|\cos|\log$ (III)

$\langle \text{var} \rangle ::= x|y|z$ (IV)

$\langle \text{num} \rangle ::= \langle \text{dig} \rangle . \langle \text{dig} \rangle \mid \langle \text{dig} \rangle$ (V)

$\langle \text{dig} \rangle ::= 0 \mid 1 \mid 2 \mid 3 \mid 4 \mid 5$ (VI)

Example: In this example, we explain the mapping process performed in GE to obtain a phenotype (mathematical function) given a genotype (chromosome). Let us suppose we have the BNF grammar provided in Figure 4 and the following 7-gene chromosome:

21-64-17-62-38-254-2

According to Figure 4, the start symbol is $S = \langle \text{expr} \rangle$, hence the decoded expression begins with the non-terminal:

$$Solution = \langle \text{expr} \rangle$$

Now, we use the first gene of the chromosome (i.e. 21) in rule I of the grammar. The number of choices in that rule is 3. Hence, the mapping function is applied: $21 \text{ MOD } 3 = 0$ and the first option is selected $\langle \text{expr} \rangle \langle \text{op} \rangle \langle \text{expr} \rangle$. The selected option substitutes the decoded non-terminal, giving the following expression:

$$Solution = \langle \text{expr} \rangle \langle \text{op} \rangle \langle \text{expr} \rangle$$

The process continues with the codon 64, used to decode the first non-terminal of the current expression, $\langle \text{expr} \rangle$. Again, the mapping function is applied to the rule: $64 \text{ MOD } 3 = 1$ and the second option $\langle \text{preop} \rangle (\langle \text{expr} \rangle)$ is selected. So far, the current expression is:

$$Solution = \langle \text{preop} \rangle (\langle \text{expr} \rangle) \langle \text{op} \rangle \langle \text{expr} \rangle$$

The next codons (17, 62, 38, 254 and 2) are decoded in the same way. After codon 2 has been decoded, the expression is:

$$Solution = \exp(x) * \langle \text{var} \rangle$$

At this point, the decoding process has run out of codons, and we need to reuse codons starting from the first one. This technique is known as wrapping and mimics the gene-overlapping phenomenon in many organisms [33]. Applying wrapping, we

use gene 21 to decode $\langle \text{VAR} \rangle$ with rule IV. This result gives the final expression of the phenotype:

$$Solution = \exp(x) * y$$

Apart from performing parameter identification, in conjunction with a well-defined fitness function, the evolutionary algorithm is also computing mathematical expressions with the set of features that best fit the target system. Thus, GE is also defining the optimal set of features that derive into the most accurate model.

Adding time dependence: Previously shown grammars allow us to obtain phenotypes that depend on a certain number of variables (e.g. x, y, z). We could use the previous method to predict variables that depend only on the current observation of other magnitudes, such as server power [34].

Models created this way can be used to predict magnitudes without memory and the data used for model creation consists of samples. Temperature, however, is a magnitude with memory, i.e. the current temperature depends on past temperature values. Thus, the data used for model creation need to be a time series. By properly tuning our grammars, we can add time dependence to the variables in the phenotype, so that past values can be used to predict the variable a certain number of samples ahead.

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